

Analyzing the Feasibility of Transforming Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) Scales into Gelatin in Reducing Food Waste in Fish Markets

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Abstract

This study investigates the feasibility of transforming tilapia scales into a gelatin to be able to reduce fish waste in the market and create it into a health beneficial product. In the Philippines, tilapia is one of the most consumed fish in the market, and its scales are usually discarded despite having important factors like collagen, a protein that can be converted into gelatin through hydrolysis. In this experiment, tilapia scales were collected, cleaned using salt and vinegar, and boiled into a pot full of water with pandan leaves to extract the collagen. Following this, the collagen mixture was separated into two samples, one being with xanthan gum and the other being without. This was then refrigerated overnight to observe the differences in consistency, smell, texture, and overall quality. The results showed that sample one successfully formed a gelatin-like substance due to the collagen extracted from the scales. However, the second sample with the xanthan gum formed an uneven and heterogeneous appearance, indicating a clumpy texture. Although both products were not suitable as a lubricant for joints, the data collected demonstrated that tilapia scales can still be used as consumable gelatin.

Keywords

Tilapia scales; Fish waste management; Collagen extraction; Fish gelatin; Food waste reduction; Circular economy; Sustainable biomaterials; Philippines

Introduction

Tilapia scales contain a large amount of collagen, which actually benefits the human body because it provides strength, elasticity, and supports the joints, muscles, and other tissues. The collagen came from the structural protein found in connective tissues from animals. In this experiment, the collagen goes through a process called hydrolysis, where its tight structure breaks down into small protein units, that is gelatin. This gelatin has viscoelastic properties. This means that it behaves like a liquid and a solid, and can act as an effective lubricant as it reduces friction between bones during movement.

This topic is important because it reduces waste by reusing tilapia scales instead of discarding them. It offers a low-cost, sustainable source of collagen that can be converted into gelatin, which may help lubricate joints. Since tilapia is familiar and affordable in the Philippines, this study provides an eco-friendly way to support both environmental sustainability and community health.

We chose this study because it is practical and makes better use of abundant tilapia scales. It shows how collagen in the scales can be transformed into gelatin using heat and mild acids. This method is low-cost, accessible, and helps address the problem of food waste. Tilapia is one of the most common fish in the Philippines, and its scales are usually thrown away but they contain collagen, a protein that can become a jelly-like substance. When fish are bought, the scales are removed and often discarded when cooking. Instead of letting these go to waste, they can be reused and turned into gelatin that can be used as joint lubricant. In this study, tilapia scales were made into a jelly using salt, vinegar, banana leaves, water and then turned into gel with hot water. The purpose is to test if this gel can work as a natural joint lubricant while also helping reduce food waste.

Background of the Study

Tilapia is one of the most common fish in the Philippines, and its scales are usually thrown away but they contain collagen, a protein that can become a jelly-like substance. When fish are bought, the scales are removed and often discarded when cooking. Instead of letting these go to waste, they can be reused and turned into gelatin that can be used as joint lubricant. In this study, tilapia scales were made into a jelly using salt, vinegar, banana leaves, water and then turned into gel with hot water. The purpose is to test if this gel can work as a natural joint lubricant while also helping reduce food waste.

Research question

Can reusing tilapia fish scales help reduce waste while creating a product with health benefits?

Hypothesis

The mixture will create gelatin and then the collagen extracted from tilapia scales can be used to create a mixture that helps lubricate the joints.

Review of Related Literature

- “In conclusion, the findings of this study demonstrate that the scales of Giant gourami, Nile tilapia, and Common carp, when pre-treated with a 3% (v/v) Averrhoa bilimbi acid solution, can be utilized to extract commercial gelatin with good functional properties and yield.” (Syandri et al., 2024). This study analyzed fish scales that create gelatin to be used as a lubricant, and in their investigation it was demonstrated that Tilapia may be employed and converted into gelatin.
- “Marine organisms such as fish, jellyfish, sponges, and other invertebrates harbor a significant source of collagen and are highly advantageous over other sources, as they are metabolically compatible, lack religious constraints and are free of animal pathogens [27,28,29,30].” (Geahchan et al., 2022).
- “Collagen from fish does have a higher absorption rate than collagen from cattle. The reason for this is that the peptides are smaller and thus more easily absorbed by the body.” (Jafari et al., 2020). This supports the use of fish scales as a sustainable collagen source, since their naturally high bioavailability makes them suitable for processing into effective lubricants.
- “Fish collagen is easier for digestion and adsorption than bovine and porcine collagen thanks to its low Hyp content and TM and has already gained popularity in the cosmetic industry.”(Gaikwad & Kim, 2024). This highlights the potential of fish scales as an ideal source for producing collagen-based lubricants due to its fast digesting and absorption.
- “The overall collagen output from Tilapia fish scales was 42%.” (Shalaby et al., 2023). This research high yield shows that tilapia scales serve as an efficient and

abundant collagen source, making them highly suitable for developing collagen-based lubricants that rely on consistent and sustainable raw material production.

- “This study has shown that improved yield of collagen was obtained when the concentration of acetic acid was 0.5 M, Volume of acid of 100mL, soaking time of 120 minutes and time and buffer concentration of 10 mL.” The current study is an attempt to optimize the process variables to obtain the highest collagen yield per gram of fish scales.” (Makgobole et al., 2024). This study highlights how fish scales can be efficiently processed through different methods and processed to maximize collagen extraction.
- “Fish scale is a unique natural biomaterial mainly composed of type I collagen and hydroxyapatite.” (Qin et al., 2021).
- “When you slow-cook fish scales for hours, a process known as hydrolysis occurs and produces gelatine. This form of collagen breaks down into smaller, soluble fibres of collagen peptides after prolonged cooking. Calcium phosphate, which boosts bone health, is also released” (Libai, 2025). This process shows how fish scales can be easily converted into usable collagen.
- “Hydrolysis is a chemical reaction in which a chemical compound is broken down by reaction with water.” Hydrolysis is a chemical reaction where water is used to break down a compound into two or more products” (Parekh et al., 2011). This is the scientific term of the process to get the collagen from the fishscales.
- “Compared to collagen from animals, collagen from fish scales has advantages such as fat-free, antibiotic-free and prion-free [7].” (Hou et al., 2022) This statement shows the safety and purity benefits of making fish-scale collagen a more reliable and cleaner raw material.
- Banana leaf was used in this experiment due to its waxy coating which prevents the tilapia jelly from sticking to the pot, additionally the banana leaf provides antibacterial properties which kills some of the bacteria in the scales. (Etimes.In, 2025)
- Tilapia is rich in amino acids like glycine and proline, which contribute to collagen synthesis and improve skin elasticity and joint flexibility which would help in lubricating the joints. (*Fish Gelatin: Benefits, Uses, and Everything You Need to Know - Ingreland, 2025*)

- Vinegar was used in our experiment to reduce the fishy odor by breaking down trimethylamine that causes the smell, it can also reduce the sliminess so the lubricant would be more smooth. (*Cleaning Fish*, n.d.)
 - The salt was abrasive and helped in scrubbing and loosening the scales, it also helps in removing debris and making sure the fish scales were clean to be applied as lube. (Facebook source)
 - The jelly was used in our experiment for the lubricant gel to be more viscous, we also wanted it to have benefits such as collagen. (Jafari et al., 2020)
 - Lavender essential oil was added to reduce or mask any remaining fishy odor from the fish-scale jelly. It also introduces a pleasant scent and is known for its calming and soothing aromatherapeutic effects. (Mori et al., 2016)
 - Gelatin made from tilapia skin is found to contain amino acids like hydroxyproline, alanine, glycine, and proline, that can help gelatin be more firm and strong, although this study has used skin instead of scales, it continues to prove that gelatin from tilapia could still function effectively. (International Journal of Food Science and Technology, 2010)
 - This study proves that Tilapia could perform well as an effective gelatin alternative producing a safe, functional gel with high strength that can even be edible and nutritious. (Osiriphun et al., 2022)
 - Gelatin and hydrolysates from tilapia scales have great functional properties that could provide health benefits and even help protect against oxidative damage. Shiao et al., 2021)
 - Collagen and gelatin can carefully be extracted from tilapia scales and produced a measurable protein absorbance, proving that gelatin from tilapia scales could be a great source of natural and beneficial gelatin. (Md Zin et al., 2019)
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Methods

Materials and Equipment

- Tilapia Scales - 100g
- Salt - $\frac{1}{2}$ tablespoon
- Vinegar - $\frac{1}{3}$ cup
- Water - 1.78 Liters (Total)
- Xanthan Gum - 6oz
- Bamboo Essential Oil - 2 drops
- Banana Leaf - $\frac{1}{2}$ piece
- Pot
- Measuring cups
- Scissors
- Strainer
- Bowl

Variables

Independent Variable – Xanthan Gum

Dependent Variable – Viscosity

Controlled Variables – Amount of fish scales, amount of vinegar and salt, boiling time, type of leaves, amount of water used

Procedures

1. Wash 100g of fish scales in a bowl thoroughly.
2. Put 2 cups of water with $\frac{1}{2}$ tablespoons of salt and $\frac{1}{3}$ cup of vinegar.
3. Soak the scales for 30 mins.
4. After 30 minutes, repeatedly wash the scales until the water is clear, then strain.
5. Transfer the scales into a pot with $\frac{1}{2}$ a piece of a whole pandan leaf then cut it up into strips as a base.
6. Add 1.28 liters of water and bring it to a boil with a lid ajar for 2 hours.
7. Once finished, strain the scales from the collagen mixture and split the mixture into two.
8. Add 6oz of Xanthan Gum to one of the mixtures in small segments until fully dissolved.

9. Lastly, store both variables in the fridge overnight and wait for results.

Results

Properties Observed	With Xanthum Gum	Without Xanthum Gum
Color	Pale yellow	Pale yellow
Texture	Clumpy and thick	Smooth gelatin
Odor	Bamboo essential oil	Bamboo essential oil
Consistency	Lumpy and slimy	Firm and jelly-like
Appearance	Clumps formed in mixture	Uniform structure

Discussion

This study concluded that tilapia scales are a sustainable source of collagen that can be used to create gelatin as a lubricant for the joints. This research aims to address the problems of food waste in the Philippines, specifically from tilapias, as it is one of the most consumed fish in the market. According to related studies and literature, the high amount of collagen found in tilapia scales can be converted into gelatin through a process called hydrolysis. Moreover, collagen from fish has a higher absorption rate than collagen from cattle. These studies support the possibility and potential to gain a useful gelatin-like substance with lubricating properties.

To conduct the study, the tilapia scales were cleaned with vinegar and salt for 30 minutes and then boiled with banana leaves for 1 hour. The resulting liquid was strained and split into two samples. One sample contained xanthan gum, while the other did not, to compare the viscosity between the two mixtures.

The observations revealed distinct patterns in the physical properties of the two samples. The gelatin containing xanthan gum appeared clumpy, thick, and uneven with visible lumps. In contrast, the gelatin without xanthan gum exhibited a smooth, firm, and consistent jelly-like texture. These differences suggest that xanthan gum significantly alters

the viscosity and texture of fish-derived gelatin. Scientifically, this can be explained by xanthan gum's polysaccharide structure, which can form gel networks that trap water irregularly, resulting in clumping, whereas pure collagen gelatin forms a more uniform matrix upon cooling.

The comparison between the two groups aligns with literature on gelatin and hydrocolloid interactions, which shows that additives like xanthan gum can modify gel strength and texture depending on concentration and mixing method. Additionally, this study demonstrates that collagen can be effectively extracted from tilapia scales and transformed into gelatin, highlighting its potential in reducing food waste while providing health benefits for joint lubrication. The findings reinforce previous research on fish collagen as a highly bioavailable alternative to mammalian collagen, confirming its applicability in functional food and nutraceutical development.

Conclusion

The results of the experiment show that reusing tilapia fish scales can help reduce waste while creating a product with potential health benefits. During the experiment, the mixture formed a gelatin-like substance due to the collagen in the scales. Though, the results showed that the mixture was not suitable as joint lubricant as originally hypothesized because we were able to make a proper gel lubricant. Instead of using it as lubricant it would be better to use it as a food product similar to gelatin or gelatinous bone broth. This product could still provide health benefits due to the bioactive peptides and proteins it has that are beneficial to the body. While the hypothesis that the collagen mixture could be used as lubricant is rejected, we found it could still be reused to make gelatin properly. This supports our idea that recycling fish scales to reduce waste and create a useful health product. Further testing with different bases and emulsifiers may help determine if it could be used as another type of product in the future.

Recommendations

1. Researchers recommend not to add Xanthan gum into the mixture. Due to the powder clumping up in the mixture and not mixing in smoothly. If it is to be tried again, add the powder in small amounts.

2. Don't add scented products to the mixture if the intended use is consumption, we recommend liquid flavorings instead.
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